

Experimental

The following procedure was adopted for the detection of oils.

To one ml of oil, first one ml of the aldehyde solution (0.4 g., in 100 ml of ethanol) and then one ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The mixture was allowed to stand for 5 min and then warmed. The colour before and after heating was noted. Observations made are recorded in the following table :

Sl.No.	Oil	TABLE	
		Colour	
		Initial	After warming
1.	Groundnut oil	No change	No change
2.	Sesame oil	violet	violet
3.	Mahuwa oil	purple	Deep purple
4.	Mustard oil	Light pink	Pink
5.	Coconut oil	No change	No change
6.	Linseed oil	Light pink	Light pink
7.	Hydrogenated groundnut oil	No change	No change
8.	Whale oil	pink	pink
9.	Seal oil	pink	pink
10.	Cod liver oil	pink	pink
11.	Butter fat (Ghee)	No change	No change

Deep and distinct colours are developed in case of mahuwa and sesame oils and it has been observed that these oils can be detected with a very small quantity of the reagent. With these two oils the colour deepens on warming. Similar colour change has also been noticed when mahuwa or sesame oil is present as one of the components in a mixture of oils.

The possibility of the use of *p* NN-bis-2'-cyanoethyl-aminobenzaldehyde in the detection of sterols is being worked out.

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2,4-Dihydroxy ketones and 2,4-Dihydroxy ketoximes as indicators for the Direct CyDTA titration of Ferric ions

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MARPLE¹ showed the superior accuracy of CyDTA compared to the direct EDTA titration of iron. According to him the end point with chrome Azurol S is much more easily determined than that with thiocynate or sulphosalicylic acid. It is to be noted however, that milligram-amounts of aluminium react with chrome Azurol S to give a violet colour which obscures the end point for the iron titration. The conditions for the use of thiocynate indicator are very restrictive. According to Martinez², with sulphosalicylic acid and tiron results are high upto 4%. The present paper reports the use of 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy-propionophenone, 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone oxime and 2,4-dihydroxy propiophenone oxime as indicators for the direct titration of iron using CyDTA.

Indicator Solutions :

1% solutions were prepared in 95% ethanol. The solutions were stable upto 4 weeks.

Observations :

2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy propiophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy butyrophenone, 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone oxime, 2,4-dihydroxypropionophenone oxime and 2,4-dihydroxybutyrophenone oxime give violet colours with ferric ions. Preliminary studies indicated that 2,4-dihydroxybutyrophenone and its oxime are not satisfactory indicators; hence the remaining four compounds were investigated in detail.

Colour Change :

If solution containing ferric ions is taken in a beaker and four drops of the indicator solution were added, the solution becomes violet. There is a sharp colour change on titration with CyDTA from purple to deep yellow at the end point.

Effect of pH :

When an aliquot of Fe⁺³ is titrated with CyDTA, iron can be estimated accurately in the pH range 1.0-2.0. However, it should be noted that below pH 1.5, the colour of the solution at the end point is of a slightly lighter shade. Hence it is advisable to add slightly more indicator (about four drops).

Effect of indicator concentration :

Titration were carried out with different concentrations of the indicator (0.5%, 0.75%, and

1.0%) and it was found that an addition of 2 drops of 1% indicator solution gave satisfactory results.

Effect of Temperature :

The titration could be satisfactorily carried out in the temperature range 15°–50°.

Lowest Concentration of Iron :

0.001 *M* solution of ferric nitrate could be satisfactorily titrated with 0.001 *M* CyDTA by using these indicators. It is interesting to note that with 2,4-dihydroxy acetophenone and 2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone oxime the end point can be detected even in 1 ml. titration volume of 0.001 *M* solution of ferric nitrate, thus microtitration with CyDTA is feasible with these indicators.

Effect of Foreign Ions :

The titration of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.0. At 1.4 mg. concentration of iron, 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of UO₂²⁺, 20 times excess of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Be²⁺, Pd²⁺, 10 times excess of Ag⁺, Ni²⁺, CO²⁺, 5 times excess of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺ and an equal amount of Cu²⁺ could be tolerated. Mn²⁺, Zn⁴⁺, Th⁴⁺ and anions forming stable complex with iron, such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Synthetic solutions containing more than one foreign ions were also analysed with the help of these indicators at pH 1.0.

Applications :

An indigenous iron ore having the following percentage composition was also analysed by the suggested procedure.

Fe₂O₃ 92.8; Al₂O₃ 1.54; SiO₂ 3.07; CaO 0.3; TiO₂ 0.1; MgO 0.28; P 0.10; S 0.03.

The observed value of ferric oxide content is 92.75% which is in good agreement with the Fe₂O₃ content of the ore.

A drug 'Ferro Folsan' manufactured by Messrs Kali-Chemie, Hannover, Germany containing 40.18%, FeSO₄ was also analysed by the suggested procedure, and the results obtained indicated the presence of 40.1% FeSO₄ which is concurrent with the content of the drug.

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